

PROBLEMS OF ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF AN INSURANCE COMPANY

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Annotation: The article highlights the problems connected with the revival of insurance in Uzbekistan. Recommendations for improving the insurance system are presented.

Key words: insurance, insurance services, insurance premiums, insurance payments, business processes.

In the modern economy, the importance of the insurance system and its main component, the insurance market, is increasing. Firstly, in world practice, the insurance system is one of the largest sources of investment in the economy during the redistribution of funds of economic entities. Secondly, insurance is one of the main forms of risk management that have an upward trend. Thirdly, ensuring the protection of the property interests of insured persons contributes to ensuring economic and financial stability, the process of expanded reproduction. The experience of developed countries testifies to the increasing role of insurance in the effective solution of many socio-economic problems.

In the Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on the priorities of the country's development for 2019, it is noted that "... it is necessary to continue reforms in the banking and financial system at an accelerated pace, widely introduce modern market mechanisms in it"

In this regard, the relevance of scientific research on improving the efficiency of the insurance system and business processes of insurance organizations is increasing.

The development of insurance relations is a strategically important task in the activities of modern economic systems. A stable insurance system stimulates the development of the national economy.

In this regard, first of all, there is a need to attract additional investment resources to the financial services market, determine the directions of development of the insurance system, and develop market relations in the field of insurance.

The insurance system is a complex of economic relations for the formation and distribution of the insurance fund to ensure the continuity of the reproduction process and insurance protection of the property interests of economic agents. If we interpret the concept of an insurance system more broadly, it also provides for social types of insurance, including pension insurance, types of insurance that have the function of long-term accumulation, as well as mutual insurance.

The analysis of the mechanism of the insurance system makes it possible to identify its impact on all economic processes in the country, to consider how the interests of the consumer of its services are satisfied. At the same time, it is important to analyze quantitative and qualitative indicators of the development of the insurance market and assess the level of economic and legal regulation of insurance relations.

The following indicators are used for this purpose:

- the volume of insurance premiums collected by insurance organizations;
- the amount of insurance payments made by insurance organizations;
- the number of insurance organizations operating in the market;
- concentration of the insurance market (Herfindahl-Hirschman index);
- the amount of capital formed by insurance organizations.

As of January 1, 2019, 30 insurance companies were registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan, of which 24 companies operate in the field of general insurance, 6 companies in the field of life insurance. In 2014, the volume of insurance premiums amounted to 439.1 billion soums, in 2015 – 515.7 billion soums, in 2016 – 692.6 billion soums, in 2017 – 927.6 billion soums, in 2018 it amounted to 1.6 trillion soums, an increase of 4.7 times compared to 2013.

Serious changes have taken place in the activities of insurance organizations that regularly demonstrate high performance in the insurance market of Uzbekistan. The level of concentration in the field of general insurance has decreased. The share of the leading three insurance companies decreased by 5.7 percent to 38.1 percent. The share of the first five organizations in the market increased by 57.5 percent, but this is 2.4 percent lower than last year. The level of concentration of organizations in the top ten and operating in the field of general insurance also decreased by 1.9 percent to 80.9 percent. The decrease in the level of concentration of organizations in the top ten is a positive result of the availability of conditions for free competition in the market.

The main task of the state control in the insurance sector in the country is to prevent the emergence of large players on the market that can influence the development of market mechanisms of competitiveness and the actions of other market participants, insurers and consumers of insurance services, lead to monopoly prices.

This approach includes the analysis of qualitative and quantitative parameters of the insurance system. The Herfindahl-Hirschman Indices (HHI) are used to identify a player in the market with a high level of concentration. They allow us to judge the effectiveness of competition mechanisms.

If HHI is less than 1000, the level of concentration in the market is low, this means that it is permissible to acquire, merge and merge companies. Using the Herfindahl-Hirschman index (HHI), when determining the level of diversification

and concentration of the insurance portfolio in insurance organizations, a mechanism for ensuring the financial stability of the insurance market and insurance organizations can be proposed.

The analysis of the insurance market of Uzbekistan has shown that there are positive trends in the national insurance market in the country. But since most of the insurance premiums are mortgaged property insurance, it is difficult to assess the real situation in the insurance market.

There are opportunities to activate the development of the national insurance system. It is necessary to increase entrepreneurial activity among individuals in this segment of the financial services market, increase the capitalization of insurance companies, strengthen state control over the activities of insurance companies.

The low level of capitalization of insurance companies has a negative impact on the financial stability of the insurance company.

One of the ways to solve this problem is to regulate the entry and promotion of foreign insurance companies into the domestic market.

There is an imbalance in the infrastructure of the insurance system. Currently, the institute of brokers almost does not carry out its activities in the insurance market of Uzbekistan.

As of January 1, 2019, 30 insurance companies and 3 insurance brokers operate in the country, and dozens, hundreds of intermediaries for insurance companies work in economically developed countries. The Institute of Brokers functions as an intermediary reinsurance in international insurance companies, and it is important to develop the coordination of state regulation of the activities of insurance brokers.

The investment potential of the national insurance system is insufficient and it is necessary to increase the investment activity of insurance companies. The role of the insurer as an institutional investor is of great importance for the development of the economy. Insurance companies of Uzbekistan failed to prove themselves as institutional investors. In 2018, 88.6 percent of the total investments were placed in

corporate securities and deposits, having a low level of profitability. To enhance the role of insurance companies as institutional investors, they must place assets in long-term investments with high profitability.

In the conditions of an innovative economy, the importance of regulatory institutions and self-government bodies is growing. Self-government in insurance activities as the regulation of insurance activities without the participation of state control bodies is called upon to play an important role in enhancing the participation of insurers in the development of investment activities.

As world practice shows, this function is performed primarily by associations of insurers and other public organizations.

It should be emphasized that the practice of self-government cannot be opposed to state control. Self-government complements the regulation of insurance relations by the state and increases the effectiveness of such regulation. Self-government can serve as an intermediary between an insurance company and a consumer of insurance services in resolving various contradictions and conflict situations. In the grassroots practice of insurance, the presence of the institution of an "arbitrator" is relevant. The activity of such an independent body, which resolves disputes before resolving cases in court, has a positive impact on insurance activities.

The main factor in the successful development of the national insurance system is the availability and improvement of market infrastructure. In this regard, it is important to carry out financial engineering of business processes in an insurance company.

The methodology of business processes of insurance organizations is subordinated to the solution of the following tasks:

- strategic planning of activities is provided, which should determine promising areas for the development of the insurance company;
- there is an opportunity to create an organizational structure that will optimize the activities of the insurance company, as well as its structural divisions;

– it becomes possible to implement operational management at all stages of the insurance company's activities.

The analysis of business processes provides, first of all, cost reduction.

In the process of reengineering, the organizational structure of an insurance company can be simplified, various resources can be redistributed, and the quality of services can be improved. Reengineering of business processes in an insurance company for a certain time, for example, every five years, will allow for changes in the insurance company taking into account changes in external factors.

The modern electronic digital economy assesses risks directly affecting the financial stability of insurance organizations as accurately and correctly as possible, ensuring insurers are provided with information with a wide coverage and reveals many opportunities for insurance activities. At the same time, it becomes possible to identify factors that directly affect the formation of a qualitative risk assessment model and forecasting the probability of occurrence of insured events.

The experience of implementing such systems in the West shows that smart insurance products have made it possible, for example, to reduce the level and number of road accidents on the roads, to increase the overall level of road safety, to reduce car owners' expenses for insurance and fuel, as well as to improve the ecological condition of cities. In the field of medicine, where the diagnosis of the disease at an early stage is the key to effective treatment, these systems make it possible to reduce medical expenses of clients, and insurance companies are allowed to take measures aimed at providing insurance coverage and its payment. Similar trends are observed in the field of property insurance of individuals.

It is advisable to further improve the insurance services market in the following areas:

– to improve the methods of concluding contracts with clients using business process tools in modern insurance;

– to improve the methodological base based on conceptual approaches of engineering and reengineering to reduce the level of unprofitability in insurance organizations;

– to achieve financial stability of the insurance market and insurance organizations on the basis of qualitative and quantitative analysis of the diversification of the insurance portfolio and determination of the level of concentration;

– implement telematics systems in insurance products, which allows you to formulate possible price parameters for the occurrence of an insured event.

The implementation of such practical recommendations will contribute to the improvement of the insurance system and the mechanisms of its functioning and thereby the implementation of the tasks outlined in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021.

Used literature.

1. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, December 28, 2018, www.uza.uz

2. Adamchuk N.G. The world insurance market on the way to globalization // Moscow: ROSSPEN. 2004. 591 p.

3. Logvinova I.L. Mutual insurance as a method of creating insurance products in the economy // Moscow: Ankil. 2010. 248 p.

4. Orlanyuk-Malitskaya L.A. Insurance: Textbook // Moscow: Yurayt. 2010. 828 p.

5. Orlova I.A. Insurance in the BRIC countries // Management in an insurance company. 2009. No. 2. p. 46.

6. Turbina K.E. Trends in the development of the world insurance market // Moscow: Ankil. 2000. 320 p.

7. Tsyganov A.A. Modern mechanisms of regulation of the insurance services market /A.A. Tsyganov, E.I. Vasiliev // M.: RAGS under the President of the Russian Federation. 2004.

8. Chernova G.V. Fundamentals of the economy of an insurance organization for risky types of insurance // S.P.: Peter. 2005. 240 p.

9. Chudinov S.A. Taxation of insurance activity in the leading countries of the European Union // Insurance business. 2010. No. 5. p. 52.

10. Yuldashev R.T. Essays on the theory of insurance. Retrospective analysis of development // Moscow: Ankil. 2009. 248 p.